

A Green Structure Taking Into Account the Landscape and Environmental Factors of a Suburban Space in a City on the Southern Shore of the Mediterranean Basin

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ABSTRACT

Faced with a strong demographic surge, the city of Skikda and its outskirts have experienced the horrors of uncontrolled urbanization. It distorted all transitions between urban areas and industrial areas which were initially agricultural areas. This poor structuring of space has caused a "physical pollution" very badly felt aesthetically. It is for this reason that it seemed essential to us to carry out a study on the potential of the suburban space of the city of Skikda which includes the *jebel Mouadher* and a portion of the *Safsaf plain*. To achieve this result, we first carried out an assessment of the potential of the site and, secondly, we defined the main lines of development of a green structure that best meet the requirements of the landscape and environmental factors of the perimeter study.

Keywords: urban risks, qualitative method, landscape, city, Algeria

CITATION:

Fadel, Djamel and Azzouzi, Amar (2019). "A Green Structure Taking Into Account the Landscape and Environmental Factors of a Suburban Space in a City on the Southern Shore of the Mediterranean Basin." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 5, No. 4: pp. 30-43. (Oct. – Dec. 2019); ISSN: 2415-0371. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3877616

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The prevention of urban risks by green spaces is one of the least studied subjects and which deserves very special attention from the scientific community, especially in developing countries where the lack of this equipment has reached worrying thresholds. In the case of Algeria, the objective of controlled urban development with respect for sustainable development is clearly displayed in legal texts but absent in reality. Capital of petrochemicals, Skikda, a coastal city in eastern Algeria, can illustrate this theme in a relevant way. Faced with a strong demographic surge, the anarchic urbanization of this city and its periphery has distorted all transitions between the various urban, industrial zones more particularly those of *Hamadi krouma* and *El Hadaïek* which were initially devoted to agriculture. This poor structuring of our study perimeter does not reveal any visibility between urban, industrial and agricultural landscapes. It has caused visual pollution

which is very badly felt aesthetically by the alarming degradation of the natural environment and the living environment of its population. It is for this reason that it seemed essential to us to carry out a study highlighting a qualitative evaluation plan on the potentials of this site taking into account landscape and environmental factors. This landscape study allows us to best respond to the type of landscaping of these spaces which will have the role:

- ✓ Transition between on the one hand the urban fabric of Skikda and the peri-urban agricultural zone of the Safsaf plain and on the other hand between the vast industrial zone represented by the petrochemical platform and the urban zones of Skikda and its periphery (Hamadi Krouma and Hamrouche Hamoudi);
- ✓ To slow down the urbanization of the city towards the industrial zone and to protect it from the sources of pollutants generated by the petrochemical complex of more than 2000 hectares of surface;
- ✓ Social or recreational and leisure role for the population of the city of Skikda, which has a significant deficit in green spaces.

In the context of our work, we used a qualitative estimation method based on a visual approach to assess the potential of the study site (Fortin, 2002 and 2008; Badouna et al., 2014).

2.0 PRESENTATION OF THE STUDY SITE

The study site, which includes the entire Mouadher jebel and a portion of the Safsaf plain, is located at the interface of the various agglomerations of Skikda, Hamadi Krouma, El Haddaiek and the petrochemical industrial zone (Fig.1). This urban, industrial and agricultural landscape grouping is based on the coexistence of three types of communication routes: maritime, rail and road. The study site occupies an area included in a quadrilateral at the following coordinates:

- ✓ 6 ° 54 Longitude East- 6 ° 57 Longitude East
- ✓ 36 ° 5 Longitudes North - 36 ° 15 Latitude

Fig.1. Situation in the study area

This suburban space which is the subject of our study makes a transition between a portion of the urban fabric of Skikda and the petrochemical pole which covers an area of more than 2000 hectares whose profile is that of a fairly polluting zone (Fadel et al., 2009 and 2016) grouping several units. It is considered to be a diffuse source of air pollution (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2. Units of the petrochemical complex

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study methodology consists of a zoning of the area into several landscape units defined by the following criteria:

- ✓ Topography;
- ✓ Plant cover;
- ✓ Housing;
- ✓ Artificialization, humanization;
- ✓ Hydrography;
- ✓ Visual quality.

After having identified the major groups, we carried out an internal analysis which led us to identify the components of the sub-units. The external analysis carried out from neighboring and affected areas allows us to structure them. The criteria which have proven to be necessary for the apprehension of the sub-assemblies are:

- ✓ Discovery on the ground, accessibility - natural accidents;
- ✓ Visual constants or rupture at sub-unit or landscape level
- ✓ Surrounding;
- ✓ Inventory of areas whose characters are to be reinforced for the elements
- ✓ Positive and to minimize for negative elements;
- ✓ Inventory of significant elements which must be taken into account when development.

All these operators that we have identified will constitute a basis of study to consider the particular uses of the units, taking into account their characters and their sensitivity as suggested (Craik, 1975; Gaudreau et al., 1986; Cossin and Piegay, 1999 and Gagnon et al., 2006). To approach the study, we put ourselves in the place of a pedestrian. We took the roads outside the area in order to understand the site as a whole. To get the details, we walked inside the area, walking along the existing routes. For the visual study, the points of view are decisive. They allow an observer to appreciate the overall value of a landscape (Clark, 1974; Griselin et al., 1999 and Fadel et al., 2013). Their location and number depend on the degree of openness of the visual field and the size of the study site as suggested by many authors (Fadel, 2012 and 2016; Fortin, 2002; Domon et al., 2003 and Djelailia et al., 2017). We only used open visual fields. We have thus identified eight (08) points of view:

- ✓ 07 points of view internal to the landscape unit of Jebel Mouadher;

✓ 01 point of view external to the landscape unit of the study site located in the landscape unit represented by the safsaf plain (Table 1).

✓
TABLE 1. Characteristics of views

Situation from the point of view	Nature of the visual field	Direction of visual field	Degree of opening of the visual field (° C)
North sector Cliff	Open	N, NE et NW	180
North sector Sea facies	Open	N, NE et NW	180
North sector Sea facies	Open	NE et NW	90
North sector Sea facies	Open	SE	90
South sector Upper part	Open	NE	90
South sector Upper part	Open	SE	90
South sector Lower part	Open	E, W et S	180
Safsaf Plain	Open	NW	90

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Topographically, the study area is heterogeneous. We have distinguished two large landscape units:

- ✓ A lower part represented by the Safsaf plain;
- ✓ A medium mountain formed by the djebel Mouadher (Fig. 3).

FIG.3. Landscape units of the study site

4.1. Safsaf plain

Due to its homogeneous flatness, the plain of Safsaf presents an overall uniformity. This fairly characteristic landscape unit is easily identifiable by its plant component. The latter allowed us to detect two landscape sub-units.

4.1.1. The orchard

Unique colonial heritage of the plain, it constitutes the first identifiable place. The agricultural fabric occupied by citrus fruits presents:

- ✓ A relatively zero relief due to the uniformity of the height of the trees;
- ✓ A homogeneous structure caused by the presence of a single species of the same age;
- ✓ Outside, its boundaries appear regular and contrast sharply with the natural meadow;
- ✓ Inside this space, the visual field is closed because the tops of citrus fruits constitute an obstacle (photo 1).

4.1.2. Natural meadow

It gives an impression of monotony because its limits are not perceived:

- ✓ They are irregular over the whole extent, except its limits of the orchard which cuts sharply with them;
- ✓ The relief is zero (photo 2);
- ✓ Homogeneous structure;
- ✓ Open visual field (photo 3).

FIG. 4. Visual appearance of its sub-units in the Safsaf plain

4.2. Jebel Mouadher

It appears at first glance that the Mouadher massif splits into two large parts. Indeed, the ridge line oriented from West to East imperatively determines two large sectors.

Fig.5. The different landscape sub-units of the djebel Mouadher

A northern sector, exposed to the sea determines a natural facies:

- ✓ Human work not perceived due to the absence of the agricultural fabric caused by natural constraints: topography and erosion;
- ✓ Lack of housing;
- ✓ Dense spontaneous vegetation;
- ✓ Inaccessible rocky escarpments (cliff).

A southern sector, environment exposed to the urban fabric in which it is integrated where:

- ✓ The work of man is perceived by the presence of vegetable gardens surrounded by fences;
- ✓ Presence of precarious "slum" type housing near cultivated plots;
- ✓ Existence of access routes: roads and paths.

4.2.1. North sector

In the northern sector, the contrasts are multiplied by the play of the relief, the difference in vegetation, the variation in the visual field. These aforementioned parameters are the main threads in the determination of our subunits which are two in number (Fig. 5).

FIG.6. Visual analysis of the North sector

4.2.1.1. Cliff

Its relief imposes itself with all its indestructible power, it exaltingly forms a panoramic fringe characterized by a wide range of simultaneous views:

- ✓ On the forest massif and the bay of Stora (photo 4);
- ✓ On the northwest part of the urban fabric (photo 5; 6);
- ✓ Distant view of the sea (photo 7).
- ✓ The schist outcrops chromatically contrast with massive and diversified tree vegetation. The gray of shale rocks opposite the dark green of sempervirens cupressus and the light and shiny green of the mixture of hardwoods represented by *Fraxinus angustifolia* (Vahl.), *Acacia decurrens* (Wild.), *Phytolaïca dioica* (L.) (Photos 8 and 9).

FIG.7. The different views from the cliff

4.2.1.2. Maritime facies

Defined by the models of the terrain, this part appears visually composed of several subspaces:

- ✓ Mouadher valley (photos 10 and 11);
- ✓ The quarry (photo 12);
- ✓ Area stripped by the works (photo 13).

The chasm formed by the quarry creates a break in level between these three spaces. Difficulty in physically connecting them through a career.

Fig.8. Visual ambiance of the maritime facies

4.2.2. South sector

The more artificialized southern facies presents two large subunits defined by topography, location and sensitivity (Fig. 6).

FIG. 9. Visual analysis of the South sector

4.2.2.1. Lower part

Partially wooded, it constitutes a green network inside the city which commands it to make a junction with the two existing gardens of the "Porte de Constantine". It is an area very sensitive to any untimely urban intervention which completely distorts it by devaluing the visual quality (photos 14 to 17).

Figure10. Visual atmosphere of the lower part of the South sector

4.2.2.2. Upper part

Located in the Southeast 50 meters above the first. It includes a homogeneous visual unity (visual field open over the whole extent of the rural area and on the Bou Farès and Fekharra djebels). The urban fabric is partially perceived because of the variation in relief. This space is a transition between the rural area and the outskirts of the city. The road to the Christian cemetery allows it to be widely accessible (photos 18 to 23).

Fig.11. Visual atmosphere of the upper part of the South sector

4.3. Summaries of data

All these operators that we have identified will constitute a basis of study to consider the particular uses for each unit taking into account their characters and their sensitivity (Carlson, 1977 ; Davodeau, 2005; Fortin, 2008 and Fadel et al 2010).

4.3.1. Landscape unit on the Safsaf plain

The arrangement and distribution of the plant material was decisive in the variation of the visual field which was either closed or open. Any change in the vegetation could modify the visual field which is defined by several authors (Zube et al 1976; Neuray, 1982; Fadel et al, 2010, 2012 and 2016). When the visual field is closed, the gaze is blocked and can only extend to our immediate surroundings with a perception of details. Inside the orchard, the plantations were dense. They were the main visual barrier. When the visual field is open, one has a distant perception. The rupture of the tree and herbaceous vegetation of the two units, allowed us a surface vision and the spread of our view. The most distant elements appear by their volume (djebel Mouadher, djebel Bou Farès and Bou Yala). On the other hand, the closest elements are better perceived (upper parts of the industrial area). To make a coherent and harmonious whole of the plain, it is important to provide visual or other transitions between these subunits and integrate them into the surrounding landscape by the following actions:

- ✓ Link the natural meadow to the orchard by pedestrian paths and by establishing centers of interest (play equipment, rest areas) to take advantage of its topography and make people forget the monotony of the plain;
- ✓ Establish a visual barrier between the industrial area and the Safsaf plain by strengthening the existing plantations or adding new ones (Fig. 7).

FIG.12. Scheme of intent

The djebel Mouadher was especially marked by an uneven relief which opposes the monotony of the plain. His landscape study seems difficult for two reasons. The first is the difficulty of finding objective data that disregards aesthetic considerations. The second lies in the choice among the many analysis criteria, those which are the most representative in the structuring of landscape subunits. The landscaping that we offer takes into account the destination of each sub-unit, their visual quality and their connection to the outside landscape (sea, urban fabric, Safsaf plain and the mountain ranges surrounding the city of Skikda).

4.3.1.1. North side

Characterized by intense erosion, this part is doomed to dense afforestation, forest type to protect the soil. In order to preserve the natural identity of this facies certain measures are to be considered.

4.3.1.1.1 Cliff

It is necessary to prohibit access to this cliff to avoid its degradation while introducing the plant, element of complementarity and contrast with the shale outcrops while preserving perspectives of the views on the forest massif and the bay of Stora.

4.3.1.1.2 Maritime facies

Protective measures are required, which firstly stop all forms of soil degradation (quarry, area stripped by the works) which disfigure the landscape. The soil should be replenished by controlled landfills aimed at eliminating the topographic break. The creation of a wooded area on the side of the petrochemical zone is essential to play the role of transition with the djebel Mouadher. Given its rugged terrain, all equipment that requires earthworks and that does not integrate well with existing ground movements should be avoided. Little subject to erosion, the Vallon du Mouadher can be converted into a natural meadow dedicated to free play.

4.3.1.2 South slope

Less eroded than the North slope, it has the advantage of being partially wooded. Very close to the urban city, this sector is very sensitive to all thoughtless interventions.

4.3.1.2.1 Lower part

The existence of easy access routes would make it the most frequented area. The slopes are relatively small, can accommodate equipment (service roads, with parking lots, playgrounds, playground etc.). Take into account landscaping by connecting the gardens of Porte de Constantine to this space, by a green flow which becomes entangled in the urban fabric. To prohibit any construction which could destroy IT.

4.3.1.2.2 Upper part

Transition space between the lower part and the rural area, it includes a homogeneous visual unit whose quality must be preserved by preserving visual corridors in the rural area and the mountain range of Djebel Bou Fares, Fakhara, El Alia by setting up place of green screens, except at the limits of the field of view. They can also play the role of firewall. It is necessary to mark the transition between the rural area and the lower part by connecting the plant components of the two areas.

4.4. Practical implementation and proposals

4.4.1. Characterization of the djebel Mouadher block and its plot

The criteria used for the division of homogeneous blocks and their plots are:

- Floor ;
- Topography and exposure;
- Existing vegetation;
- Accessibility;
- Aptitude for development.

The objective of the reforestation of this area is mainly focused on soil protection; no mechanical preparation is advisable except the opening of pots, this in order to preserve the plantcover which has a protective effect on the soil. However, we do not exclude the aesthetic factor of the site. This desired effect can be obtained by a judicious choice of forest species and by appropriate planting methods. It will mainly be intended for a walk forest where special attention must be paid to the choice of equipment. Over its entire extent, the djebel Mouadher presents a heterogeneity in terms of geomorphological, pedological point of view marked by the variation in soil depth and visual (Fig. 1).

FIG.13. Plot of Djebel Mouadher

In order to better respond technically to all these problems, we deemed it necessary to divide this area into several plots for which we offer the following types of intervention:

- Plot A: very eroded area and exposed to sea winds. The priority intervention will mainly be to protect the soil against water erosion. The depth of the soil is relatively small, varying from 0.20 to 0.30 meters.

- Plot B: makes a transition between the plain and the urban fabric. The erosion is little accentuated. The soil is fairly deep 0.5-0.7 meters. Area dedicated to the creation of landscaped areas, offering a wide range of interesting views of the mountain ranges and the Saf Saf plain (Fadel et al., 1987,). She is particularly predisposed to walking and resting.

- Plot C: less subject to natural constraints, this area is characterized by deep, moist soil exceeding more than one (01) meter. Agro-climatic factors are favorable to it and make it a site of choice at the site of an arboretum. The valley floor contained in this parcel is not very sensitive to trampling and therefore allows a significant number of visitors. We see it as a natural meadow for free play. Some species will be planted in bouquets to ensure the visual transition between the wooded plots. They create shade and freshness for users.

- Plot D: adjoining the city, it requires a more acute aesthetic consideration than the other plots. Because of its protected exposure and its artificialized facies, it is possible to introduce exotic plants in reasonable proportions and in certain particularly sheltered places. This plot is very sensitive to any construction that distorts its function of transition and relay with the existing plantations of the urban fabric at the entrance to the city called Porte de Constantine. Certain administrative protective measures must be taken.

4.4.2. Choice of species in the study area

The choice of species is driven by a set of agro-climatic factors limiting the growth of forest species in the study area. In addition, preference was given to species that are very suitable in the cork oak area and to those species that have proven themselves in the El Kala region located at the far east of the Algerian coast with climatic factors similar to those of Skikda. For the choice of species we used the new flora of Algeria from Quezel and Santa (1962). The species likely to develop are:

Pinus pinaster (Ait.)
Pinus halepensis (Mill)
Pinus pinea (L.)
Cupressus sempervirens (vat.horizontalis) (L.)
Ailanthus glandulosa (Mill)
Robinia pseudo - acacia (L.)
Fraxinus oxyphilla (L.)
Populus alba (L.)
Quercus .faginea (Lam.)
Eucalyptus camaldulensis. (Dehnh)
Eucalyptus globulus (Labill.)
Olea europa (L.)
Celtis austrails (L.)
Platanus acerifolia (Aiton) Willd.
Acacia decurrens (J.C. Wendl.)
Melia azedarach (L.)
Salix alba (L.)

5.0 CONCLUSION

As part of our work, the qualitative approach, based on visual appreciation, allowed us to highlight the landscape potentials from different points of view of the study area. Indeed these potentials identified on this site taking into account the landscape and environmental factors are really a database necessary to undertake any future development. The djebel Mouadher was especially marked by an uneven relief which opposes the monotony of the plain. His landscape study seems difficult for two reasons. The first is the difficulty of finding objective data that disregards aesthetic considerations. The second lies in the choice among the many analysis criteria, those which are the most representative in the structuring of landscape subunits. The landscaping that we offer takes into account the destination of each sub-unit, their visual quality and their connection to the outside landscape (sea, urban fabric, Safsaf plain and the mountain ranges surrounding the city of Skikda). The proposed plan defined the main lines of the development and specifies the actions to be taken immediately. Each will require further technical study. The study of the environment, more particularly the pedological and geomorphological study, enabled us to identify the priority developments on the djebel Mouadher, which consists of restoring the soil before it is intended for the public.

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